

Effect of hydrostatic pressure on superconducting properties and flux dynamics of Fe and Cr substituted NbSe₂ single crystal

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Abstracts:

Magnetization measurements have been used to determine the effect of magnetic impurities (Fe and Cr) on the Larkin–Ovchinnikov (LO) 3D collective pinning model in NbSe₂ single crystals under the hydrostatic pressure (P) up to 1 GPa [1,2]. We found that the pressure can induce a transition from the regime where pinning is controlled by spatial variation in the critical transition temperature (δT_c) to the regime controlled by spatial variation in the mean free path ($\delta \ell$) [3]. Furthermore, T_c and low field J_c are slightly induced, although the J_c drops more rapidly at high fields than at ambient P. The pressure effect enhances the anisotropy and reduces the coherence length, resulting in weak interaction of the vortex cores with the pinning centers. Moreover, the P can induce the density of states, which, in turn, leads to enhance in T_c with increasing P. The intrinsic disorder in pure NbSe₂ single crystals shows δT_c flux pinning; however, the extrinsic disorder created by doping atoms in NbSe₂ shows $\delta \ell$ flux pinning and application of P. Both $\delta \ell$ and δT_c core pinning strongly enhance the coupling between the vortices in the randomized pinning potential, which makes the 3D magnetic fluxes into 2D nature. P enhances the T_c with the rates of dT_c/dP is higher compared to the ambient. The magnetization data are used to establish a vortex phase diagram. The nature of the vortices has been determined from the scaling behaviour of the pinning force density extracted from the J_c – H isotherms and demonstrates the point pinning mechanism.

References

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